

IMPROVING TASKS FOR TESTING STANDARDS OF NEW INSTALLING SOFTWARE SYSTEMS

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Abstract: the continuous increase on profit of business runners, who implemented technology, especially software to their business systems vividly illustrated how software engineering is crucial for attaining financial aims for companies and expand their services. According to this the following thesis is outlining the importance as well as required standards of significant tool of software engineering, namely software testing process for initial implementation of programs.

Key words: software, software engineering, testing system, software testing, standards of software testing process, AI.

Information systems, it may be said, are critical components of any civilization. The impulse to record information dates back thousands of years, to the time when people first began drawing on stones.

However, the phrase "information system" refers to the process of recording and displaying information in a systematic manner. Such behaviors are common in large civilizations such as ancient Egypt, Greece, and Rome. The evolution and use of information technology (IT) have resulted in the introduction of new generations of software applications. Computer-based information systems (software systems) have had a significant impact on our behavior and the way we go about our daily lives.

Even though there are many information systems that do not require computers, such as a tiny library's card filing system or a manager's contact list, practically all modern information systems use or might use computers to accomplish part of their duties.

Moreover, while we will reference information systems on occasion, the focus of this module is on the software components of an information system and how to create software that can be used reliably by others. Software is an essential component of computerized information systems. Without the underlying software, the system cannot accomplish what its users expect, and if the program malfunctions, consequently does the information system.

Therefore, one of older version, legacy software is frequently of low quality by today's standards: inextensible, complicated, poorly documented, and developed

in languages that are no longer widely used. Unfortunately, because it serves essential business operations, such legacy software has a lengthy lifespan. As a result, old systems must be reengineered in order to be usable in the future. Consider this to be a steady development of legacy software. The following adjustments below, are frequently carried out for one of the following reasons:

[1]

The advantages of introducing new software are not always obvious. The individual (or persons) who are contemplating the introduction or extension of a software may be quite optimistic about the prospective advantages of using the new software, like as offering "better service" and "greater control".

Nevertheless, because the present (manual or partially software-based) method is unlikely to damage a corporation, the benefits of the new software may be difficult to evaluate. Indeed, unless the program is well-designed and well-thought-out, it may provide no overall advantages. Many companies are motivated to study the creation of new or expanded software systems in their operations because of the potential for considerable advantages and the differences information systems have made in other firms. Because organizations, their information systems, and the software they use are complex, the costs and benefits of information system and software development are difficult to assess and quantify.

These systems are difficult to analyze, develop, and implement. As a result, extensive research has been conducted into the interaction between information

systems and software inside businesses, as well as information system and software development.

In general, potential benefits may be classified into two types:

Tactical benefits

- which improves the day-to-day running of an organisation or group in measurable terms.

Strategic benefits

- about improving nature of abilities of a group or organisation. With a new software system, a business may be able to offer their customer new service. Or by examining the information held, could new customers or products could be identified.

[1]

Individuals do not frequently welcome change for the sake of change. There is always danger associated with changing old procedures - to paraphrase an English proverb "If it is not broken, do not repair it!". The most basic reason might be because consumers appreciate the sight or sound of new technology, and a corporation wants to be viewed as being on the "leading edge" of technology. Installing a new high-tech software system enhances the company's image. Companies might take advantage of this chance to enjoy some of the additional benefits that a new system may provide. Alternatively, a corporation may learn that new technology allows them to access new processing facilities and processes.

Additionally, all new installing software system must have to be checked and implemented by modern standards of testing systems as they are referred to the way of safer service later on. That is why the vast majority of companies even pay for professionals to test their new systems before applying to real work conditions.

Typically, firms build new software systems in response to external factors. Costs may be growing, but new software may help to cut them. According to all, the following tips to improve testing systems are recommended:

- offering a framework for developing test plans, designs, test cases, procedures, logs, and reports;
- creating higher quality standards, identifying, implementing, analyzing, and validating process and product software quality metrics;
- assisting in the direction of Software Verification and Validation plans; providing a framework for establishing system specs (SRS).

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